

Effects of Bullying and Violence Exposure on Civic Education Students' Academic Performance in Katsina State Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of bullying and exposure to violence on civic education students' academic performance among senior secondary schools in Katsina state Nigeria. The study was guided by four objectives from which four research questions and four null hypotheses were generated and analyzed. Correlational research design was adopted, with a sample of three hundred and seventy (370) randomly selected from a total population of seventeen thousand three hundred and twenty-eight (17,328) SSII students from twenty-five (25) public senior secondary schools of Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance. Two instruments tagged, Bullying Behaviour Questionnaire (BBQ), and Students Violence Questionnaire (SVQ) were used to collect data. Furthermore, Civic Education 2018/2019 Qualifying Examination Questions of the Education Resource Centre, Katsina (2022) were used as a measure of the students' academic performance. The data collected were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) and independent sample t-test at 0.05 level of significance. Results revealed significant relationship of bullying and academic performance ($r = 0.595$), significant relationship of exposure to violence to civic education students' academic performance ($r = -0.508$), significant difference of bullying between male and female civic education students ($t = 3.272$), and significant difference of exposure to violence between male and female civic education students ($t = 8.089$). Based on the findings, it was recommended that Government should be organizing seminars/workshop for both teachers and students on personality traits and their impact on students' academic performance particularly those dealing with negative behaviours; teachers and Counselling Psychologist should help students develop a positive/high self-efficacy through affirmation. Finally, parents should inculcate the habit of self-confidence in the mind of their children/wards by affirming to them whenever they do the right thing and correct in love whenever they do wrong. This will improve the students' determination in their academic performance.

Keyword Bullying, Violence, Civic Education, Academic Performance

Introduction

Education is a tool that plays the pivotal role of bringing about political, moral, human and socio-economic change in the lives of citizens, for full participation in any given national function. Education is of great value to every nation; therefore, it attracts considerable attention to the family and the community. Its aims are to equip students with knowledge, skills and attitude that will enable them render useful services to themselves and society. According to Asiabaka (2019), education is the key to national development, which provides the intellectual capability needed to harness human and material resources for scientific and technological advancement.

Bullying is the act of repeatedly engaging in hostile behavior with the intention of injuring another person physically, mentally, or emotionally. Over time, the conduct is repeated, or has the potential to be repeated. Bullying can range from one-on-one bullying to mobbing in which the bully has one or more "lieutenants" who are eager to assist the principal bully in their bullying activities. Peer abuse is a term used to describe bullying in schools and at work. It involves things like issuing threats, spreading rumors, physically or verbally assaulting someone, and purposefully excluding someone from a group. Therefore, School bullying can be physical, verbal or emotional and is usually repeated over a period of time (Aliero, Mainagge and Tsagem, 2023). Likewise, in the bullying situation, one can play different roles, namely the bully and the victim (Boulton & Smith, 2014). This relationship implies an unbalance of power between individuals, where the first (the bully) exerts dominance and coercion over the second (the victim) (Olweus, 2012). Bullying can happen in a quiet way where only the perpetrator and the victim interact, or it can happen in a social context and in high-profile conditions, such as in a school. In this context, some colleagues may witness bullying behaviors by reacting pro-socially either by defending the victim and expressing disapproval to the aggressor or by supporting the aggressor. Failure to react at all may also express tacit approval of that behavior. Bullying

is a behavior that affects all the subjects involved and manifests complex interdependencies leading to a negative impact on various dimensions of the individual. If it occurs in the school context, it influences the attitude of the actors in that context (Van der Ploeg, Steglich, & Veenstra, 2020). Bullying can occur in many ways, the most common being physical, verbal, material, relational, and cyberbullying.

The nature of the issue of 'seniority' in our schools had given some students chances to punish others, which when carefully looked into sometimes can be categorized as a disguised aggression (Tsagem, 2013). Violence consists of actions, words, attitudes and socio-cultural damages that prevent people from achieving their full human potentials as a family. The act could be deliberate or non-deliberate (Lareau, 2013). Violence in the family is a deliberate pattern of abusive and accusative tactics used by one member(s) of the family in an ultimate relationship to obtain or maintain power and absolute control or independence within the family. According to Dutton (2014), violence in the family covers a broad range of controlling behaviours which typically involve fear, harm, intimidation and emotional deprivation which might affect children's academic performance in schools. Violence in the family could be physical, psychological, sexual, violence based on gender and socio-economic status of parents (Ganley, 2015).

Violence is an intentional use of physical force or power to cause harm, injury, or death to oneself, others, or objects. It can include behaviors like physical fights, weapon use, property destruction, or even self-harm. Violence among students can occur within the school environment (bullying, physical altercations) or outside of it (community violence, exposure to domestic violence). The relationship between aggressiveness, violence, and academic performance has been a subject of interest in psychological and educational research. Studies have consistently shown a negative association between high levels of aggressiveness and academic performance (Bettencourt, Farrell & Maheri 2016). Aggressiveness, characterized by hostile behaviors and anger, can lead to disruptions in the classroom environment and hinder the learning process for both aggressive individuals and their peers. Moreover, research has highlighted a potential link between increased exposure to violence, either as a witness or a victim, and decreased academic performance (Cook, Williams, Guerra, Kim & Sadek 2016). The negative impact of violence on academic outcomes may be attributed to the psychological distress it causes, which can impede concentration and motivation to succeed academically. To address these concerns, interventions that promote anger management, conflict resolution, and a positive school climate have been suggested to mitigate the negative effects of aggressiveness and violence on academic performance (Swearer et al., 2017). It is crucial for educators, parents, and policymakers to recognize the importance of addressing these issues to create safe and conducive learning environments for students.

This research is motivated by the need to provide insights that could inform policies and interventions aimed at creating safer, more supportive learning environments that foster academic success despite external challenges. Moreover, it is significant because it addresses the broader implications of violence and bullying on the educational outcomes of students, which in turn affects their future prospects and the overall development of society. Civic Education is essential in building a democratic and peaceful society, and any factors that hinder students' ability to succeed in this subject must be addressed. By exploring the effect of bullying and exposure to violence on academic performance, this research aims to contribute to the understanding of how these negative experiences impact learning and to identify strategies that schools, communities, and policymakers can use to mitigate these effects. Academic performance as defined by Makinde (2019) refers to level of performance in written works and exams. Against this background, the study will focus on the effect of bullying and exposure to violence on civic education students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Katsina state, Nigeria.

The problem revolves around the detrimental impact of bullying and exposure to violence on the academic performance of civic education students in senior secondary schools in Katsina state. Despite being recognized as significant issues in educational settings, there is a lack of comprehensive understanding regarding the specific ways in which bullying and exposure to violence affect students' academic performance. Furthermore, the unique socio-cultural context of Katsina state may introduce additional complexities that influence the prevalence and effects of these phenomena. Without a clear understanding of the relationship between bullying, exposure to violence, and academic performance in civic education, effective intervention strategies cannot be developed or implemented to mitigate these challenges and promote a safer and more conducive learning environment for students in senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance. The stakeholders affected by this problem include students, parents, educators, and the broader community. Students experiencing bullying and violence may struggle to perform well academically, leading to potential long-term effects on their educational and career opportunities as a result of this situation many attempts were made by ministry of education officials, teachers and other stakeholders such Parent Teachers Association but the problem persist. Parents deeply concerned about their children's emotional well-being and academic progress, sought ways to support them effectively. Educators face the challenge of maintaining a safe and conducive learning environment for all students, while also addressing the individual needs of those

displaying aggressive behavior. The community, too, seeks to address the root causes of violence and its influence on academic performance, aiming to create a nurturing environment for its young members. The research observed that senior secondary school students are facing much failure in civic education, which is expected to happen as a result of aggressiveness and violence that is taking place among the students and it is expected to improve their academic performance. Thus, the study aimed at determining the effect of bullying and exposure to violence on civic education students' academic performance among senior secondary schools in Katsina zonal Education Quality Assurance.

Objectives of the study:

The objectives of this study are:

1. To find out the relationship between bullying and students' academic performance in civic education in senior secondary schools of Katsina zonal Education Quality Assurance.
2. To find out the relationship between exposure to violence and students' academic performance in civic education in senior secondary school of Katsina zonal Education Quality Assurance.
3. To find out the difference of bullying between male and female civic education students in senior secondary schools of Katsina zonal Education Quality Assurance.
4. To find out the difference of exposure to violence between male and female civic education students in senior secondary schools in Katsina zonal Education Quality Assurance.

Research Questions

The following research questions are designed to guide the conduct of the study:

1. What is the relationship between bullying and students' academic performance in civic education in the senior secondary schools?
2. What is the relationship between violence and students' academic performance in civic education in the senior secondary schools?
3. What is the difference of bullying between male and female civic education students in the senior secondary schools?
4. What is the difference of exposure to violence between male and female civic education students in the senior secondary schools.

Hypotheses:

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between bullying and students' academic performance in civic education in senior secondary schools of Katsina zonal Education Quality Assurance.
2. There is no significant relationship between exposure to violence and students' academic performance in civic education in senior secondary schools of Katsina zonal Education Quality Assurance.
3. There is no significant difference of bullying between male and female civic education students in senior secondary schools of Katsina zonal Education Quality Assurance.
4. There is no significant difference of exposure to violence between male and female civic education students in senior secondary schools of Katsina zonal Education Quality Assurance.

Methodology

The correlational research design was used for this study, and the rationale behind the selection of this research design is because it seeks to establish what association exists between two or more variables, and also indicates the direction and magnitude of the relationship between the variables involved (Nworgu, 2013).

The population of this study comprised all the public senior secondary school year two (SS II) students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina. The Zone has a total number of twenty-five (25) public senior secondary schools for both males and females under the state Ministry of Education, with a total population of seventeen thousand three hundred and twenty-eight (17,328). The researchers' choice of public schools is due to the fact that they share common characteristics such as teachers, instructional materials and other facilities that will aid teaching and learning. Bullying Behaviour Questionnaire (BBQ) adapted from Muli (2022), Students Violence Questionnaire (SVQ) and the students Civic Education 2018/2019 Qualifying Examination Questions of the Education Resource Centre, Katsina (2022) as measure of the student academic performance were used as the instruments for data collection. A pilot study was conducted to ascertain the validities and reliabilities of these instruments. An internal consistency reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha

technique and indices values of .789 and .879 were respectively obtained and analysed at 0.05 level of significance using (SPSS) version 23.0.

Results

The instruments were administered to three hundred and seventy (370) sampled students, and all the three hundred and sixty (370) questionnaires were successfully completed and returned. The 370 questionnaires returned consist of one hundred and ninety-two (192) male students and one hundred and seventy-eight (178) female students.

Table 1: Shows Summary of Students' Population by Gender and Percentage

S/N	Gender	Number	Percentage
01	Male	192	52%
02	Female	178	48%
Total		370	100.0

Table 1 presents the gender of sample students in the study, which shows that 192 (52%) males participated in the study and 178 (48%) females participated in the study. Thus, the table indicates that more males participate in the study than females.

Hypothesis One

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between bullying and students' academic performance in civic education in senior secondary schools of Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (r) was used to test this hypothesis and the result of the test was presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Correlation between Bullying and Students' Academic Performance

Variables	N	Pearson <i>r</i>	<i>p</i> -value	Decision
Bullying	370	.595	.000	Significant
Academic Performance				

Table 2 shows that Pearson's $r = 0.595$ and p -value is .000 at 0.05 level of significance. Since the p -value of .000 is less than the alpha value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected which indicates that there is significant relationship between bullying and students' academic performance in civic education in senior secondary schools of Katsina zonal Education Quality Assurance. It signifies that as the bullying lowers, the academic performance of the students increases.

Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between exposure to violence and students' academic performance in civic education in senior secondary schools of Katsina zonal Education Quality Assurance.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (r) was used to test this hypothesis and the result of the test was presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Correlation of Exposure to Violence and Students' Academic Performance

Variables	N	Pearson's <i>r</i>	<i>p</i> -value	Decision
Exposure to Violence	370	-.508	.000	Significant
Academic Performance				

Table 3 shows that Pearson's $r = -0.508$ and p -value is .000 at 0.05 level of significance. Since the p -value of .000 is less than the alpha value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected which indicated significant relationship between exposure to

violence and students' academic performance in civic education in senior secondary schools of Katsina zonal Education Quality Assurance. This further indicates that as exposure to violence increases the academic performance of students decreases.

Hypothesis Three

Ho3: There is no significant difference of bullying between male and female Civic Education students in senior secondary schools of Katsina zonal Education Quality Assurance.

The *t*-test of independent samples was used to test this hypothesis and the result of the test was presented in table 4.

Table 4: Difference in bullying between male and female Civic Education students

Variables	N	Mean	SD	<i>t</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Decision
Male	192	37.96	8.213			
				3.272	.001	Significant
Female	178	35.88	8.797			

Table 4 shows that *t*-value = 3.272 and *p*-value is .001 at 0.05 level of significance. Since the *p*-value of .001 is less than the alpha value of 0.05 the null hypothesis was rejected, which indicated significant difference in bullying between male and female Civic Education students in senior secondary schools of Katsina zonal Education Quality Assurance. Furthermore, the table also indicates that female students are less bullied than the males.

Hypothesis Four

Ho4: There is no significant of exposure to violence between male and female Civic Education students in senior secondary schools of Katsina zonal Education Quality Assurance.

The *t*-test of independent samples was used to test this hypothesis and the result of the test was presented in table 5.

Table 5: Difference in exposure to violence between male and female Civic Education students

Variables	N	Mean	SD	<i>t</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Decision
Male	192	41.77	8.867			
				8.089	.000	Significant
Female	178	34.45	7.809			

Table 5 shows that *t*-value = 8.089 and *p*-value is .000 at 0.05 level of significance. Since the *p*-value of .000 is less than the alpha value of 0.05 the null hypothesis was rejected, which indicated significant difference in exposure to violence between male and female Civic Education students in senior secondary schools of Katsina zonal Education Quality Assurance. Furthermore, the table indicates that male students are more exposed to violence than the females.

Discussion of Findings

In line with the relationship between bullying and academic performance of students, the finding of the study shows the significant relationship between the two. This is supported by Goms and Costa (2020) on bullying's negative effect on academic performance. Bullying carries great harm for all involved, undermining academic performance as well. Results showed that the bullying situation itself, didn't significantly explain the academic performance of those involved. These results highlight the importance of the educational agents' attention to the existing behaviors in their classrooms, not only to the disruption established in each classroom's environment, but as a possible sign of an involvement in the existing bullying dynamics.

In line with the relationship between violence and academic performance of students, the finding of the study shows significant relationship between the two. This is inconsonant with Nwafor and Odoemelam (2022) who examined the effect of violence on academic performance of SS III students in public secondary schools in Abia State. It specifically investigated whether physical and psychological violence affect the academic performance of students. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. From a population of 6280 teachers, Taro Yamene's Model was used to draw a total sample of 349 teachers comprising of 178 males and 171 females which were randomly selected. Violence effect on academic performance of students' questionnaire (VEAASQ) was used as instrument for data collection. Findings from the study revealed that male and female respondents have common position that physical violence as well as psychological violence have effect on students' academic

performance. Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended among others that; every school should be assigned with professional guidance counselor, in-service training for counselling should be introduced for teachers in the state so as to equip them the requisite skills and organization of intermittent school-community partnership programmes for stakeholders.

In line with the difference in bullying between male and female civic education students, finding of the study shows significant difference between the two. This agrees with the findings of Obregón-Cuesta et al., (2022) on bullying in adolescents: differences between gender and school year and relationship with academic performance. School bullying is a phenomenon of unjustified aggression in the school environment that is widespread throughout the world and with serious consequences for both the bully and the bullied. The objectives of this research were to analyze the differences between the different bullying categories by gender and academic year in primary and secondary education students, as well as their relationship with academic performance. The study's results showed statistically significant differences in gender and academic year, indicating a greater number of boys in the role of the bully/victim and girls in that of non-bully/non-victim. The most aggressive students were in the 2nd year of ESO (12–13 years old). Regarding academic performance, statistically significant differences were obtained that confirm the hypothesis that performance or average grade varies according to the category of bullying in which students find themselves. The academic performance of the non-bully/non-victim and those in the victim category was found to be higher than that of bullies and bully/victim students.

In line with the difference in exposure to violence between male and female civic education students, finding of the study shows significant difference between the two. This was supported with the findings of Rahman (2018) study on exploring violence in boys and girls as related to their academic performance and residential background in Bangladesh. Stratified random sampling technique was used and total 80 respondents constituted the sample of the study. Thus, the study used a $2 \times 2 \times 2$ factorial design consisting of two levels of gender (boy/girl), two levels of academic performance (high grade/low grade) and two levels of residential background (urban/rural). It was found that regardless of gender, boys expressed more aggression than girls. Similarly, regardless of academic performance, students with high academic grade showed more aggressive behavior than low academic grade students. Finally, students of urban areas showed significantly more aggressive behavior than rural areas students. Thus, the differential treatment in gender, academic performance and residential background provides a new dimension in understanding aggression in rural and urban boys and girls. They therefore, recommend for a comparative study between rural advantaged and disadvantaged schools, as well as urban advantaged and disadvantaged schools regarding aggression in children.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study concluded that decrease in bullying leads to increase in academic performance. Likewise, increase in exposure to violence decrease academic performance. Male students are more bullied than the females. Furthermore, it was found that male students were more exposed to violence than their female counterpart.

Recommendations

From the study's findings, it could be seen that problems exhibited by exposure to violence and bullying hinders academic performance among senior secondary school students in our schools. The government, parents, guidance and counselling officers, teachers and the society, as well as students themselves have a role to play in order to tackle these issues. Thus, based on the findings of the study, the researchers therefore make the following recommendations:

1. Government should be organizing seminars/workshop for both teachers and students on personality traits and their impact on students' academic performance particularly those dealing with negative behaviours;
2. Teachers and Counselling Psychologist should help students' develop positive/high self-efficacy through affirmation. This is why guidance and counselling unit must encourage, in all schools especially senior secondary schools, for a better student academic performance;
3. Teachers and school administrators should adopt diverse techniques for managing different personalities in the school environment, with particular focus on addressing issues related to exposure to violence and bullying. As these traits can influence both the perpetrators and victims of bullying, ensuring a more supportive and understanding approach tailored to individual needs would be paramount.
4. Parents should inculcate the habit of self-confidence in their children/wards by affirming to them whenever they do the right thing and correct in love whenever they do wrong. This will improve the students' determination in their academic performance.

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